

SANGUINICOLIASIS IN CYPRINID FISH

by
Kua Beng Chu
Fisheries Research Institute,
11960 Batu Maung, Penang,
Malaysia.

Sanguinicoliasis is the disease caused by blood flukes that live in the vascular system of freshwater and marine fishes. It has a simple life cycle and consists of a molluscan intermediate host with fish as the definitive host. *Sanguinicola armata* is considered as one of the most serious pathogens to carps in Asia. Recently this species was observed in locally produced grass carp, *Ctenopharyngodon idellus*, fingerlings. The transmission of *S. armata* among locally bred grass carp fingerlings indicates that some of the indigenous snails could act as intermediate hosts. Preliminary studies of the infection of the local snail indicated an early sign for the distribution of this parasite to become more widespread and thus will become a threat to fish farming industry in Malaysia. Due to its economic importance, studies on the life cycle and morphology of larval stages of *S. armata* have been carried out.

Plate 1: The definitive host, grass carp (*C. idellus*) fingerlings of *S. armata*.

In these studies, the infected and uninfected grass carp fingerlings (Plate 1) were used as definitive hosts, and the snail, *Gyraulus convexiusculus* was used as intermediate hosts. The snail *Gyraulus convexiusculus* (Plate 2) were bred in the laboratory and the uninfected juvenile snails from the second and third generations were used as intermediate hosts. For the infection trial,

30 uninfected snails were exposed to 10 infected grass carp fingerlings in 13L aquarium for a duration of 24 hours and later transferred into another aquarium and left for about 2 weeks. The snails were later taken out individually and kept in a 15ml test tube containing dechlorinated water and a light source on top to stimulate the emergence of the cercariae. After 1-2 hours, the cercariae were collected for infection trials in fish. A 40L aquarium was used where 102 uninfected grass carp fingerlings

Plate 2: The intermediate host, snail *G. convexiusculus* of *S. armata*

were exposed to 300 cercariae for the duration of 24 hours. Results showed that 74.48% of 102 grass carp fingerlings were infected with 3.92% mortality. The eggs of *S. armata* were found in various organs such as gills, heart, kidney and liver. However, the mature eggs were only active in the gill tissue. These eggs hatched out into miracidia which swam freely in the water before penetrating the snail as intermediate host. The snails were infected on day one with immature mother sporocyst which later developed into daughter sporocysts and cercariae. All of the *S. armata* larval stages were seen in the digestive glands of snail tissue between day 10 until day 14. The furcocercous cercariae emerged from the infected snails swam actively alternating with period of passive floatation and infected the definitive host by penetration through the abdominal area. Overall, 40 to 43 days are needed for *S. armata* to complete their life cycle.